

ESTIMATION OF CLAY CONTENT USING THE FIRST AND SECOND NORM OF THE IDEALISED FALL CONE FLOW CURVE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents two models that predict the quantity of active clay content within the soil matrix. The first model utilizes the ratio of the second to the first norm (distance factor) of the idealized fall cone flow curve. In contrast, the second model is based on the correlation between liquid limit and clay content. These models were developed by analyzing 307 Atterberg limits and clay content test results, a comprehensive data collection from thirteen published literature. The models were validated using 55 test results from four additional published literature. The predicted clay content was within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 given in AASHTO T88-10.

INTRODUCTION

Clay content is typically determined using the standard procedures outlined in either BS 1377 or AASHTO T88-10. One significant limitation of current clay content determination methods is their inability to differentiate between active and inactive clay, implying that the methods determine total clay content, which includes both inactive and active clay content. This paper addresses this issue by proposing two models that can predict the active clay content, thereby providing a method for estimating clay content that differentiates between active and inactive clay.

The presence of non-clay clay-sized particles in the soil distorts the correlation between the liquid limit/plasticity index and the clay content. Maregesi (2023,2024) suggested that the difference between the plasticity index and the determined clay content can delineate active and inactive clay. He coined the word "clay index" to describe this difference. He suggested that inactive and active clay be delineated at a zero clay index. Soil with a negative clay index contains a substantial amount of inactive clay (clay-sized non-clay minerals) that dilutes the clay minerals' activeness, reducing the soil's clay

index to less than zero. On the other hand, soil with a positive clay index is primarily active clay, and the liquid limit/plasticity index is highly correlated with the clay content. Since plasticity is imparted to the soil by the active clay content, impliedly, the active clay content must be correlated to the liquid limit/plasticity index or any of its derivatives, such as the distance factor.

It is important to note that the mathematical modeling of the relationship between the liquid limit or plasticity index and clay content is only possible for soils with a positive clay index. In particular, this modeling becomes problematic or even impossible when inactive and active clay is included in determining the clay content. However, if the inactive clay content is separated from the active clay content, it is possible to model this relationship successfully. Since plasticity is imparted to the soil by active clay minerals within the soil matrix, any model that can predict the plasticity index can also predict the amount of clay within the soil matrix for soil with a positive clay index (Maregesi, 2023,2024).

Maregesi (2023) idealized the fall cone flow curve by postulating that a zero fall cone penetration value corresponds to zero moisture content. Thus, the soil's liquid limit fall cone flow curve can be treated as a position vector with a coordinate of $\langle 0,0 \rangle$ and $\langle LL,20 \rangle$. The idealized flow curve, which connects the original coordinate (0,0) and the liquid limit at coordinate (LL,20), can be treated as a position vector with a horizontal component equal to the liquid limit and a vertical component equal to the fall cone penetration at the liquid limit, i.e., 20 mm. He coined the word 'distance factor' to describe the ratio of the second norm (Euclidean distance) and the first norm (Manhattan distance).

The distance factor, as defined in equation 1, can be used to estimate the plasticity index of the soil (Maregesi, 2023). Therefore, it can predict the clay content within the soil matrix. To develop a model

for computing the clay content, 307 Atterberg limits and clay content test results were collected from the literature. From these, 172 test results with a positive clay index were selected for further analysis and development of the models that predict clay content within the soil matrix. The test results were taken from various sources, including Reddy et al. (2020) (45 test results), Cerato et al. (2006) (4 test results), Prakash et al. (2012) (9 test results), Sridharan et al. (2000) (4 test results), Vincent et al. (2021) (6 test results), Otoko (2014) (12 test results), Widjaja et al. (2020) (21 test results), Sridharan et al. (1986) (7 test results), Spagnoli et al. (2018) (76 test results), Afolagboye et al. (2021) (75 test results), Karakan (2020) (34 test results), Mishra (2012) (13 test results), Sridharan et al. (1988) (5 test results), and Reznik (2016) (5 test results).

$$D_f = \frac{\|L\|_2}{\|L\|_1} = \frac{\sqrt{LL^2 + 20^2}}{LL + 20} \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

- LL is the liquid limit
- $\|L\|_2$ is the second norm (Euclidian distance)
- $\|L\|_1$ is the first norm (Manhattan distance)
- D_f is the distance factor

DEVELOPMENT OF MODEL OF COMPUTING ACTIVE CLAY CONTENT

It is crucial to understand that the Casagrande cup and fall cone methods can yield significantly different results when determining the liquid limit and plasticity index, especially for clay with a high plasticity index (Wasti, 1987; Prakash et al., 2006; Ozer, 2009). This divergence becomes more pronounced for soil with a liquid limit exceeding 70, where the fall cone consistently provides a lower liquid limit value (Verástegui-Flores et al., 2014; Di Mateo et al., 2015). However, for this study, it has been assumed that both methods produce similar results.

Figure 1: Variation of clay index and distance factor

Figure 2: Variation of negative clay index and clay content

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between the clay index and the distance factor, showing a significant correlation, particularly for soil with a positive clay index. Conversely, there is no correlation between the clay index and the distance factor for soil with a negative clay index, as evidenced by Figure 2. Figure 3 confirms a strong

correlation between the positive clay index and the distance factor. This robust correlation supports the previously established hypothesis that the clay index of zero is the value that delineates inactive and active clay (Maregesi, 2023, 2024). As such, a mathematical model utilizing a distance factor as an independent variable can be used to estimate the clay content for soil with a positive clay index. The model can estimate the amount of active clay in the soil matrix for soil with a negative clay index. This makes it possible to report both active and inactive clay content when determining clay content in accordance with standard procedures stipulated in BS 1377 and AASHTO T88-10. Figure 4 shows a general trend: as the distance factor increases, the clay content increases for both soil with negative and positive clay index. However, the data are widely scattered, making it impossible to model them mathematically. Figure 5 confirms that there is no correlation between the distance factor and the clay content for soil with a negative clay index.

Figure 6 illustrates the correlation between the 'distance factor ' and the clay content for soil with a positive clay index. The graph demonstrates a strong relationship between the distance factor and the clay content. This is further supported by the high coefficient of determination of 0.8881, achieved when the data are fitted using an exponential function shown in equation 2. Given the significant correlation between the distance factor and the clay content for soil with a positive clay index, equation 2 can be utilized to calculate the clay content for soil with a positive clay index. Furthermore, this same equation can also estimate the active clay content for soil with a negative clay index. Notably, since the distance factor is determined solely by the liquid limit, Equation 2 suggests that the clay content for soil with a positive clay index can be estimated using only the liquid limit as a predictor variable by substituting D_f in Equation 2 with Equation 1.

$$\text{clay} = 378.2652(D_f - 0.6962)^{1.1177} \dots \dots (2)$$

Figure 3: Variation of positive clay index and distance factor

Figure 4: The variation between the distance factor and the clay content for soil with positive and negative clay index

Figure 5: Variation of the distance factor and clay content for soil with negative clay index

Figure 6: The correlation between distance factor and clay content for soil with positive clay index ($R^2=0.8908$)

COMPUTATION OF THE CLAY CONTENT FOR SOIL WITH A POSITIVE CLAY INDEX

To thoroughly assess the accuracy of the model presented in Equation 2, the clay content of the soil with a positive clay index was computed using this equation. The model's accuracy was checked using a residual plot, a method typically used to identify any issues with regression. Figure 7 provides a detailed illustration of the computed clay content and the residual, demonstrating that 87% of the test results are within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 specified in AASHTO T 88-10. The residual values are equally and randomly spaced around the horizontal axis.

Figure 7: Residual plot showing the difference between the determined and computed clay

Figure 8 shows a comprehensive comparison between the calculated and determined clay content, revealing that the results are randomly scattered on both sides of the line of equality, suggesting that the model fits the data reasonably well. Figure 9 presents a residual histogram, which indicates that 90% of the residuals are within the statistical testing bound of ± 12 and are symmetrical about the origin, satisfying the assumption of residual normality. The residual has

a high density of points close to the origin and a low density of points away from the origin, confirming that the residual is independent and normally distributed.

Figure 8: Comparison between the determined and computed clay content

Figure 9: Residual histogram

CORRELATION BETWEEN LIQUID LIMIT AND CLAY CONTENT

Equation 2, which can estimate the clay content within the soil matrix, suggests that liquid limit can be used as a sole predictor of clay content for soils with a positive clay index. Therefore, using the correlation between the computed clay content from equation 2 and the liquid limit, a model that estimates clay content within the soil matrix using the liquid limit can be developed, as shown in Figure 10. It can be seen that the computed clay content follows a well-defined pattern, which can be modeled mathematically using the exponential function shown in Equation 3, from which it can postulated that for most organic soils, each liquid limit is associated with the unique value of clay content. It can be seen that as the clay content increases, the liquid limit also increases. Maregesi (2023) suggested that the clay minerals can be identified using the average slope of the fall cone flow curve or liquid limit. The soil with an average fall cone slope of less than 0.16, which translates to a liquid limit of more than 125, is likely montmorillonite. In contrast, soil with an average fall cone slope of more than 0.56 or a liquid limit of less than 36 is likely to be kaolinite, while soil with an average fall cone slope within the range of 0.16-0.56 translating to a liquid limit within the range of 36-125 is illite or binary mixture of the kaolinite and montmorillonite or mixture of illite, kaolinite and montmorillonite.

It can be seen that the correlation between the liquid limit and clay content is nonlinear and can be represented using an exponential function, as shown in Equation 3. However, the correlation between the liquid limit and clay for soil with a clay content of less than 60 and a liquid limit of less than 100 can be modeled as linear, provided the soil has a positive clay index (Maregesi, 2023, 2024). As for the other models proposed for estimating the clay content (Maregesi, 2023, 2024), active clay content will be estimated if the linear model is used for estimating the clay content for soil with a negative clay index.

Figure 10: The active, inactive, and total clay content for soils with negative clay index

Figure 10 shows the correlation between liquid limit and computed clay content using Equation 2, from which it can be seen that kaolinite clay can have a maximum active clay content of about 23. In contrast, illite, a binary mixture of kaolinite and montmorillonite, or a mixture of clay minerals, can have a maximum active clay content of 65. The clay content exceeding 65% is attributed to the montmorillonite clay. However, based on analysis of the clay and Atterberg limits test results, it is noted that for soil to have a 100% active clay content, its liquid limit must surpass 550, indicating the presence of montmorillonite clay. This means that a reported clay content of 100% for the kaolinite clay, which is not uncommon, can be misleading. This study suggests that the maximum active clay content within the soil matrix is approximately 23% for the kaolinite clay. Therefore, in the case of recording a clay content of 100% for kaolinite clay or soil with a liquid limit of less than 550, the recorded clay content of 100% is due to the presence of inactive clay-sized non-clay minerals within the soil matrix. Therefore, the amount of active clay content within the soil matrix can be used to identify the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix.

$$clay = 10.5422e^{\frac{79.9548}{LL}} \dots \dots (3)$$

VALIDATION OF THE MODEL

Equation 3 is a model that can be used to estimate the clay content of soil using only the liquid limit value as the predictor variable. The model was validated using Atterberg and clay content test results with a positive clay index. The validation of the model was carried out using 55 test results from published literature, including 20 from Firinncioglu et al. (2023), 12 from Wang et al. (2022), 6 from Hayden et al., 6 from Sridharan et al. (1988), and 17 from Vinod et al. (2012). The validation test results are shown in Figure 11, which shows that 98% of the 55 test results plotted within the statistical testing bound of the clay content determination of ±12.

Figure 11: The liquid limit and clay content for 55 test results used for validating the model shown in Equation 3

CONCLUSION

The proposed mathematical models, represented by equations 2 and 3, effectively compute the soil's clay content for soil with a positive clay index. They can also compute the active clay content within the soil matrix for soil with a negative clay index, thereby facilitating the reporting of inactive and active clay content.

The linear model can estimate the relationship between the liquid limit and clay content for soil with a liquid limit of less than 120 and clay content of 60. This linear model, applicable under the condition that the soil has a positive clay index, allows for a reliable estimation of the clay content of the kaolinite and partly mixed clay minerals. However, beyond these specific values of liquid limit and clay content, the soil is classified as montmorillonite clay, and the relationship between the clay content and liquid limit takes a nonlinear form.

The active clay content of the soil imparts plasticity to the soil and is largely influenced by the mineralogical composition of the soil. Based on the analysis carried out in this study, the maximum active clay content in kaolinite soil is estimated to be 23 (Figures 10 and 11). The mixed clay, including the binary mixture of montmorillonite and kaolinite, exhibits a clay content range from 23 to 65. The active clay content in montmorillonite clay can range from 65 to 100%. It is interesting to note that a clay content of 100% is often reported for kaolinite clay. However, this is because the test determines both inactive and active clay content. The presence of inactive clay particles within the soil matrix can contain a clay-sized particle of up to 100% for kaolinite clay. The only clay mineral that can record 100% clay is montmorillonite clay, and the liquid limit of this clay soil is more than 550. Therefore, the quantity of active clay within the soil matrix can be used to identify the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix.

The proposed models in this study can compute the active clay content for soil with a negative clay index. Therefore, models presented in this study can discern the active and inactive clay content, making it possible to record both active and inactive clay content during clay content determination.

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